

FRACTURE CRITERION FOR NOTCHED CARBON CLOTH/EPOXY LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes a modified form of applying the Mar-Lin criterion for predicting the fracture stress of notched composites. The modified criterion is applied to each individual lamina, instead of being applied to the whole laminate. For carbon cloth/epoxy laminates, the laminate fracture parameter is determined as a function of the fracture parameter of each lamina. So, the notched fracture stress of a large class of laminates may be determined through the modified criterion with a reduced number of tests. The modified criterion showed good correlation with experimental data for composite laminates with circular holes.

Keywords: composite materials, carbon cloth/epoxy, notch sensitivity, laminate toughness parameter, fracture strength, failure criteria.

1. INTRODUCTION

Several criteria have been proposed to find the fracture stress of notched composite laminates. This is a very complex subject due to particular characteristics of composite materials such as notch sensitivity, formation of damage zones and delamination near notches and cracks. Most of criteria are based on plane stress analysis and on the use of experimental parameters of material and lay-up.

According to the Mar-Lin criterion [1], the laminate fracture must occur through the propagation of a crack lying in the matrix material at the interface matrix/filament. This criterion is based on linear elastic fracture mechanics and the notched fracture stress σ_N for a composite laminate is given by

$$\sigma_N = H_c (2R)^{-m} \quad (1)$$

where H_c is the laminate fracture toughness parameter, R is the hole radius and the exponent m is the value of the stress singularity at the tip of the discontinuity lying at a matrix/fiber interface.

This criterion is applied by establishing the value of m , which is considered a material property (dependent on system fiber/matrix), and establishing the average value of H_c for each laminate from experimental data. Experimental programs have demonstrated that the value of H_c is not dependent

on the notch size. The value of m depends on the shear modulus and Poisson's ratios of fiber and matrix materials. Mar and Lin [2] obtained a theoretical value of 0.26 for exponent m , while Fenner [3] obtained 0.28 for graphite/epoxy laminates. This criterion is easy to apply and has shown good correlation with results of experimental programs[4].

Mar and Lin suggested that it may be possible to correlate the factor H_c with the number of 0 degree plies of the laminate [1]. In this work, an approach is proposed to compute the value of H_c for carbon cloth/epoxy laminates with fibers oriented at (0/90) and (± 45). The approach is based on the toughness parameter of two lay-ups: one with fibers oriented at (0/90) and other with fibers oriented at (± 45). The stresses in each layer are calculated by Classical Lamination Theory. Theoretical values of H_c obtained from this approach have shown close agreement with experimental results. So, the fracture toughness parameter of a laminate with a combination of layers at (0/90) and (± 45) may be found with good accuracy. This enables the use of Mar and Lin criterion with a reduced number of tests.

2. LAMINATE TOUGHNESS PARAMETER

According to Equation 1, two parameters are necessary for the application of Mar-Lin criterion: the exponent m , which is considered a material property, and the toughness parameter H_c , which is considered a laminate property. The toughness parameter H_c must be determined experimentally for each different laminate. Due to this fact, a large number of tests become necessary.

The approach shown below proposes a small change in the original criterion. The main objective is to obtain a good estimate for the fracture stress of notched carbon cloth/epoxy laminates with a reduced number of tests.

The first step is the characterization of H_c for two types of laminates: one with fibers oriented at (0/90) and the other with fibers at (± 45). Based on the toughness parameter of these two laminates, we can find the toughness parameter of a general laminate with a combination between layers at (0/90) and (± 45).

We can define $H_{0/90}$ and $H_{\pm 45}$ as the toughness parameters for (0/90) and (± 45) layers respectively. By applying the criterion for a lamina oriented at (0/90) we have:

$$\sigma_{0/90} = H_{0/90} (2R)^{-m} \quad (2)$$

where $\sigma_{0/90}$ is the stress in the lamina (0/90) when fracture occurs and the external average stress is σ_N . Similarly, for a (± 45) degree ply we have:

$$\sigma_{\pm 45} = H_{\pm 45} (2R)^{-m} \quad (3)$$

The Classical Lamination Theory predicts a relation between $\sigma_{0/90}$, $\sigma_{\pm 45}$ and σ_N . For the sake of simplicity we admit:

$$\sigma_{0/90} = F_{0/90} \sigma_N \quad (4)$$

and

$$\sigma_{\pm 45} = F_{\pm 45} \sigma_N \quad (5)$$

where $F_{0/90}$ and $F_{\pm 45}$ may be considered as stress factors, depending on the elastic properties of material and on the proportion between (0/90) and (± 45) layers. By substituting Equations 4 and 5 in Equations 2 and 3 respectively, we have:

and
$$\sigma_N = H^* (2R)^{-m} \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma_N = H^{**} (2R)^{-m} \quad (7)$$

where

$$H^* = H_{0/90} / F_{0/90} \quad (8)$$

and

$$H^{**} = H_{\pm 45} / F_{\pm 45} \quad (9)$$

Since Equations 6 and 7 refer now to the fracture stress σ_N of the whole laminate, H^* is the laminate fracture parameter obtained from the fracture properties of (0/90) layers. Similarly, H^{**} is the laminate fracture parameter obtained from (± 45) layers. Equations 6 and 7 represent two different failure criteria for notched laminates and H^* and H^{**} are, in general, different and only one of them will be representative of the laminate macroscopic behavior.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The modified Mar-Lin criterion was compared to the results of an experimental program developed by Soriano [5]. Six different carbon cloth/epoxy laminates were used. The laminates were classified according to the percentage of layers oriented at (± 45). The laminates are described on Table 1.

Table 1. Laminate description

CODE	LAMINATE
L1	[(0/90)] ₅
L2	[(0/90) ₂ /(± 45)/(0/90) ₂]
L3	[(0/90)/(± 45)/(0/90)/(± 45)/(0/90)]
L4	[(± 45)/(0/90)/(± 45)/(0/90)/(± 45)]
L5	[(± 45) ₂ /(0/90)/(± 45) ₂]
L6	[(± 45)] ₅

The test specimens were subjected to axial tensile load at a constant speed of 1mm/min. The elastic properties obtained for a lamina at (0/90) are shown below:

$$E_1 = 73.03 \text{ GPa}$$

$$E_2 = 73.03 \text{ GPa}$$

$$\nu_{12} = 0.045$$

$$G_{12} = 6.58 \text{ GPa}$$

where subscript 1 means longitudinal direction and subscript 2 means transverse direction.

For each laminate, four unnotched test specimens were tested along with four test specimens for each of the following hole diameters: 3.18, 6.35, 9.53 and 12.70 mm.

An analysis of the stresses in each layer of unnotched test specimens has shown that laminate failure is mainly related to the failure of (0/90) layers for laminates with up to 60% of layers oriented at (± 45). Failure of laminates with 80% of layers at (± 45) is still dominated by failure of (0/90) layers, but in a fewer extent. According to this behavior, it seems to be natural to apply Mar-Lin criterion to each individual lamina, instead of applying it to the whole laminate.

The fracture toughness parameter H_c and the stress singularity m were determined for each laminate in order to get the best fit of Equation 1 with experimental data. Laminates L1 to L4 (from zero to 60% of layers at ± 45) presented an average value of 0.3 for the exponent m . This average value is representative for these laminates, as we can see in Figure 1. When the percentage of ± 45 layers is higher than 80%, the value of the exponent m falls between 0.23 and 0.24.

Figure 1. Stress singularity m for different laminates.

According to the results shown in Figure 2, the laminate parameter H^* is in close agreement with experimental laminate fracture parameter H_c . So, the failure of notched laminates with up to approximately 93% of layers oriented at (± 45) is dominated by the failure of (0/90) layers, i.e., by the parameter H^* . This behavior seems to show that even with the failure of (± 45) layers, the laminate will not fail as a whole until the (0/90) layers collapse.

Due to the procedure used to evaluate the fracture parameters H^* and H^{**} they coincide with fracture toughness parameter H_c for laminates L1 and L6 respectively.

Figure 2. Fracture parameters H_c , H^* and H^{**} as functions of percentage of ± 45 layers.

Figures 3(a) to 3(d) show the fracture stress obtained through the original Mar-Lin criterion and the modified criterion proposed. The two approaches were almost the same for laminates with 20% and 40% of layers at ± 45 . This behavior was predictable since the experimental values of H_c and those predicted by Equation (8) were in close agreement and the exponent $m = 0.3$ is representative for these laminates. Laminates with 60% and 80% of layers oriented at ± 45 also showed good correlation between the two approaches.

(a) $[(0/90)_2/(\pm 45)/(0/90)_2]$

(b) $[(0/90)/(\pm 45)/(0/90)/(\pm 45)/(0/90)]$

(c) $[(\pm 45)/(0/90)/(\pm 45)/(0/90)/(\pm 45)]$

(d) $[(\pm 45)_2/(0/90)/(\pm 45)_2]$

Figures 3(a) to 3(d). Experimental data and theoretical correlations for notched carbon cloth/epoxy laminates:

4. CONCLUSIONS

Most of criteria used for predicting the failure load of notched composites requires the determination of experimental parameters of material and lay-up. The two parameters employed by the Mar-Lin criterion, the stress singularity m and the fracture toughness parameter H_c , may be obtained with simple axial tensile tests. Another advantage of Mar-Lin criterion is that it correlates

well with experimental data for notched laminates that fail in an in-plane mode. By considering that the main disadvantage of Mar-Lin criterion is the great number of tests required for determination of the toughness parameter H_c for each laminate, the use of the modified criterion is helpful since it gives a good approximation for the laminate toughness parameter for most carbon cloth/epoxy laminates based only on the data from (0/90) and (± 45) laminates. The stress singularity m was shown to be dependent on the orientation of fibers in the laminate, but in a wide range (from zero to 60% of fibers oriented at ± 45) its value was approximately constant.

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